

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 131

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 131

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 131:0 A Song of Ascents, of David.</p> <p>Psa. 131:1 O LORD, my heart is not ^aproud, nor my eyes ^{1b}haughty; Nor do I ²involve myself in 'great matters, Or in things ^dtoo ³difficult for me. ² Surely I have ^acomposed and quieted my soul; Like a weaned ^bchild <i>rests</i> ¹against his mother, My soul is like a weaned child ¹within me. ³ O Israel, ^ahope in the LORD ^bFrom this time forth and forever.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 131:1</p> <p style="text-align: right;">שִׁיר הַמַּעֲלוֹת לְדָוִד יְהוָה לֹא-גִבָּה לִבִּי וְלֹא-רָמּוּ עֵינַי וְלֹא-הִלֵּכְתִּי בְגִדְלוֹת וּבְנִפְלְאוֹת מִמֶּנִּי : ² אִם-לֹא שִׁוִּיתִי אֹרְזֵמֹתַי נִפְשִׁי כְּנֶמֶל עָלַי אִמּוֹ כְּנֶמֶל עָלַי נִפְשִׁי : ³ יִתֵּל יִשְׂרָאֵל אֶל-יְהוָה מִעַתָּה וְעַד-עוֹלָם :</p>

References

Psalm 131:1

¹Or *lofty*

²Lit *go after*, walk

³Or *marvelous*

^a2 Sam 22:28; Ps 101:5; Is 2:12; Zeph 3:11

^bProv 30:13; Is 5:15

^cJer 45:5; Rom 12:16

^dJob 42:3; Ps 139:6

Psalm 131:2

¹Or *upon*

^aPs 62:1

^bMatt 18:3; 1 Cor 14:20

Psalm 131:3

^aPs 130:7

^bPs 113:2

Targum

Psa. 131:1 A song uttered on the ascents of the abyss. O LORD, my heart is not proud, and my eyes are not lifted up, and I have not walked in things too great and wonderful for me. ² Verily I have placed a hand on my mouth and silenced my soul while listening to words of Torah, like a weaned child at its mother's breasts; I have become mighty in the Torah; like a weaned child is my soul upon him. ³ Let Israel wait long for the LORD from now and forevermore.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

In this Psalm, King David explores the depths of his own personality and reveals the innocent quality of his trusting soul. Even though David was a King, he approached the LORD with genuine humility and self-effacement. David foresaw that the Jews were destined to languish in Exile. David understood that the way to redemption from exile was to demonstrate humility before the LORD.

Notes of the Psalm

It does not matter what your position is in society, synagogue, or church. There is no rank in Heaven. Leaders must remember this as David did. David treated his people well. Too many world leaders do not treat their citizens well nor equal. Equality is supposed to exist. The same idea exists in houses of worship. Yes, there is leadership. The leaders have to remember that every member is equal!

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

